

Invalidity of a fraud's treaty within the implications for the maritime boundary negotiations between Australia and Timor-Leste

Dr R. Herman Katimin, S.Sos., S.H., M.Si., M.H.^{1*}

Rakotoarivelo Tiana Nantenaina, S.H., M.H.²

¹Lecturer of the master of Law Study Program, Galuh Ciamis University, Indonesia

²Lawyer, Graduated in Master's degree of International Law, the Faculty of law, Padjadjaran University Bandung, Indonesia

Abstract: In 2006, Australia and Timor Leste agreed on Treaty on Certain Maritime Arrangements in the Timor Sea (CMATS) as a provisional arrangement concerning resources management in the Greater Sunrise field. However, six years later, a former agent of the Australian Secret Intelligence Service provided some information to the government of Timor Leste that Australia had intercepted the internal discussion of the CMATS negotiation in 2004. The act of espionage during the CMATS negotiation can be deemed a breach of the good faith principle according to the UN Convention on the Law of the Sea and the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969 (VCLT). This article aims to analyze interception as a breach of the duty of performing good faith principles in the negotiation process, which can serve as the basis to invalidate the arrangement. Espionage as a form of deceitful proceedings can be assumed as an element of fraudulent conduct derived from fraud under Article 49 of VCLT. The establishment of permanent maritime boundaries can be applied as a solution for both countries to achieve legal assurance for disputed resource field management, as well as involving the third party as a solution to Timor Sea dispute resolution. Timor now argues that the 2006 treaty is invalid because Australia spied on its treaty negotiators, thus gaining an unfair advantage. While spying alone does not invalidate a treaty, fraud can. It is untested whether espionage constitutes fraud.

Keywords: Law of Treaties, Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969, Fraud, good faith, espionage.

*Corresponding Author

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I. Introduction

In this article, the discussion of the law of treaties and its implications for the eventual resumption of negotiations on maritime borders between Australia and East Timor is necessary. While this article does not focus primarily on the substance of the dispute between Timor-Leste and Australia, it is vital to understand the essential background to the

disagreement between these two countries. Enormous oil and gas reserves at the core of the conflict lie in the sea between Timor-Leste and Australia in an area known as the Timor Sea. Following Timor-Leste's independence, the two States concluded the 2002 Timor Sea Treaty, later supplemented by the 2003 Agreement relating to the Unitization of the Sunrise and Troubadour Fields (IUA) and the 2006 Certain Maritime Arrangements in the Timor Sea Treaty (CMATS). None of these agreements determined the maritime boundaries of Australia and Timor-Leste. Instead, they dealt with how revenues from the oil and gas reserves in the Timor Sea, particularly the Greater Sunrise field, would be divided [1]. First, CMATS entered into force between Australia and Timor-Leste on 23 February 2007, according to Article 13 of the Convention. Second, absent a valid ground for terminating a treaty or a condition that renders the treaty invalid (or otherwise void), it is universally recognized that "every treaty in force is binding on the parties to it and must be performed in good faith"[2]. This rule goes by the ancient law latin name of *pacta sunt servanda* (promises must be kept).

On 6 March 2018, at the United Nations Headquarters in New York, the representatives of the Democratic Republic of Timor-Leste (Timor-Leste) and the Commonwealth of Australia signed the Treaty between the Democratic Republic of Timor-Leste and Australia Establishing their Maritime Boundaries in the Timor Sea (Treaty) [3]. This Treaty, assuming ratification by the parties and entry into force, brings to an end a longstanding and bitter dispute between Australia and the new republic of Timor-Leste that has its origins in Australia's treaty relations with Indonesia before Timor-Leste emerged as a fully sovereign state.

II. Literature Review

2.1 The arbitration between Timor-Leste and Australia

It's ready to consider the current arbitration between Timor-Leste and Australia in light of the law of treaties. In analyzing the conflict, it seems that Timor-Leste's ultimate goal is to have the arbitral tribunal declare that the CMATS (Certain Maritime Arrangements in the Timor Sea) is not binding on the parties, so that Australia's obligation to negotiate in good faith the maritime boundary in the Timor Sea is revived, instead of deferred until 2057. This brings us to the negotiation of the 2006 CMATS Treaty. The Treaty itself is observable for its duration until 2057, its extension of the Timor Sea Treaty until 2057, and its moratorium on all sovereign rights claims and jurisdiction and maritime boundaries for the period of the Treaty. It also exempts the parties from any obligation to negotiate in good faith on the permanent boundaries until 2057. Significantly, it provides an equal share for East Timor and Australia of revenues from the upstream exploitation of petroleum from the Great Sunrise deposits. Although this revenue-sharing agreement is more generous than before, the problem now seems to lie in how East Timor has obtained the consent of the CMATS Treaty.

Of course, Australia will argue that the cessation provision contained in CMATS Article 12 is conclusive and must be observed: *Pacta sunt servanda* (article 26 of the Vienna Convention on the law of Treaties), treaties are binding and must be performed in good faith. Australia may claim that Timor-Leste had free reign to agree or disagree with the procedural rules that govern the cessation of CMATS. In Australia's likely view, Timor-Leste gave free consent to the design and operation of the Article 12 cessation clause. For Australia, the provision was included as a way of managing the risk of international cooperation in the speculative world of resource exploitation and where the political stability of Timor-Leste over time might be feared. In addition, the length of the agreement was, in some measure, a way to provide enough time to allow for necessary capital investments and then generate a reasonable return.

To prevail in the arbitration, Timor-Leste will need to surmount the rule of *pacta sunt servanda*. It will need to demonstrate that its consent was never really given or that a particular circumstance involved in the negotiation of the Treaty means that it is invalid under the law of treaties or otherwise may be vitiated under general international law. That brings us to the reports of Australian espionage during the negotiation of CMATS. Suppose the media reports of

2014 are accurate and Timor-Leste can prove that Australia bugged the Cabinet Room of the Timor-Leste negotiated [4]. In that case, it may be possible that this Treaty (and the extension of the Timor Sea Treaty) is invalid under the law of treaties or voidable under general international law. Again, while it is impossible to know the basis of the claims Timor-Leste is asserting against Australia in the current arbitration because these proceedings are closed to public view and the written claims and arguments are not available, it is possible to make some reasonable suppositions about those claims. As a result, Australia violated customary international law by acting in bad faith, contrary to the good faith requirement, a fundamental legal principle governing relations between States. Such conduct is similar to fraud or corruption, grounds expressly recognized by the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties as vitiating the apparent consent of a State to be bound by a treaty. These rules and principles of international law apply to the provisions of the 2006 Treaty, whose purpose is to modify that of 2002; Consequently, those provisions are void and devoid of the legal effect and, therefore, cannot alter the 2002 Treaty.

2.2 Agreement of the Parties

Before getting to those suppositions, however, it is well to point out the hopeful recent signs that this maritime dispute might move back to a negotiating track for amicable resolution by the parties. Two years, it was reported that Senator Pilbersek announced that Labor would “redouble efforts to conclude good faith negotiations with Timor-Leste to settle the maritime boundaries between our two countries.”

Senator Pilbersek went on to state that if the negotiations are not successful, Australia, under a Labor government, “is prepared to submit ourselves to international adjudication or arbitration,” which would result in a legally binding outcome [5]. Under the law of treaties, it is always open for parties to a bilateral treaty like CMATS to agree to alter terms or, indeed, to end the treaty early. In making her statements, Senator Pilbersek noted that Timor-Leste had suffered decades of wear and starvation”, that “the boundary dispute has poisoned relations with our newest neighbor,” and that the Timorese are “so very disappointed that a country that supported them in their struggle for independence has ... delayed coming to a negotiation on sea boundaries”[6]. One is tempted to read into these sorts of comments some form of recognition of the old category of “unequal treaties” prominent at the end of the 19th Century and in the era of decolonization in the mid20th Century, but almost absent from treaty analysis today [7]. Be that as it may, the point is that Australia could decide to enter maritime boundary negotiations with Timor-Leste, and, Article 12 of CMATS would be no impediment.

2.3 Invalidity on Account of fraud

First, as a matter of treaty law, under Article 49 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (VCLT), to which both Australia and Timor-Leste are party, a state that is induced to conclude a treaty by the fraudulent conduct of a negotiating state may invoke the fraud to invalidate its consent to be bound by the treaty [8]. The definition of fraud in international law includes deliberately deceitful behavior in the formation of an international agreement.⁸ Spying to obtain confidential and privileged information in order to gain advantage in treaty negotiations is deceitful behavior. The issue of good faith negotiations is not merely theoretical; it has also been on the agenda of international courts. At the moment, a case is pending in the Permanent Court of Arbitration (PCA) where Timor-Leste is seeking to invalidate a treaty with Australia on the grounds of fraud [9]. Less certain, however, is whether this deceitful behavior actually induced Timor-Leste to enter the CMATS treaty. If the evidence presented proves a deceitful inducement, Australia may have the dubious distinction of being the first known state to have a treaty declared invalid on account of fraud [10]. Even if it may be argued that there is always a duty to negotiate in good faith, the problem for Timor Leste is that it is not clear whether breach of that obligation is a ground for invalidity of a treaty. It is unclear precisely what legal arguments will be advanced to support Timor-Leste’s claim for invalidity. In media reports, Timor-Leste has pointed to the principles in the VCLT as supporting its claim. Part V of the VCLT sets out

several grounds for invalidity, and Article 42(1) makes clear that such grounds are exhaustive. Of these exhaustive grounds, failure to negotiate in good faith is not included. So, absent any specific ground dealing with good faith, what other grounds for invalidity may be invoked by Timor Leste? Based on the information publicly available, one ground that may be relevant is invalidity for fraud. In this article 49 of the VCLT provides that: "If a State has been induced to conclude a treaty by the fraudulent conduct of another negotiating State, the State may invoke the fraud as invalidating its consent to be bound by the treaty".

In addition to fraud, bad faith manifests in corruptive and coercive conduct that can invoke to invalidate a State's consent to be bound by a treaty. Direct or indirect corruption of a representative of a State by another negotiating State (VCLT Article 50) means promising, offering, or giving the representative of another negotiating State an undue substantial pecuniary or non-pecuniary advantage to induce him or her to give consent to a treaty, which they would otherwise not have given [10].

Therefore, the questions to be resolved are whether the alleged acts of espionage by the Australian intelligence officials constitute 'fraudulent conduct' and whether Timor Leste has been induced to conclude the CMATS Treaty by that fraudulent conduct. Does espionage amount to 'fraudulent conduct'? There appears to be no precedent to guide this inquiry, and should Timor-Leste succeed in its claim, it will be the first State to invoke the fraud provision successfully. 'Fraud' and 'fraudulent conduct' are not defined in the VCLT. In the International Law Commission's commentary to the draft Article 46 on the Law of Treaties, which became Article 49 of the VCLT, the International Law Commission noted (on page 245, opening paragraph) that 'fraudulent conduct' includes: "any false statements, misrepresentations or other deceitful proceedings by which a State is induced to give consent to a treaty which it would not otherwise have given." Suppose a consensual agreement to reopen negotiations on the maritime boundary does not happen. In that case, which the current Australian government does not seem to be disposed to enter into, the recent arbitration is set to conclude. It is here that Timor-Leste will have to advance arguments to overcome the rule of *pacta sunt servanda*.

One possibility is an argument based on the invalidity of CMATS. The VCLT provides several grounds on which a treaty may be deemed invalid. It does this to ensure that treaties have been concluded through the proper process and by those with the requisite authority. Second, it protects the fundamental values of the international legal system. The grounds of invalidity laid down in Articles 46 through 53 of the VCLT primarily address these two issues by focusing on defects that arise in the consent of a state to be bound by a treaty that they entail [11]. The grounds of invalidity relate to the following items:

- The known impropriety of a state's consent in light of its constitutional order.
- Error, fraud, and corruption in the formation of treaties.
- Coercion of the individual negotiator or the state through a threat or use of force.
- Peremptory norms from which no new treaty cannot derogate under international law.

As we already talked about espionage above, this espionage complained of by Timor-Leste is challenging to bring within the terms of any of the grounds of invalidity with the amount of information that is available. Fraud, under Article 49, seems the most promising. A state induced to conclude a treaty by the fraudulent conduct of a negotiating state may invoke the copy to invalidate its consent to be bound by the treaty.

III. A breach of good faith in the negotiation of a treaty

According to the International Court of Justice (ICJ), the reported spying by Australia would breach its obligation of good faith under international law. Negotiations between States are an integral aspect of international relations [12]. Good faith is a thread that runs through the law of treaties. The obligation is to interpret a compact in good faith (Article 31 of the VCLT) and to perform a treaty in good faith (Article 26 of the VCLT). However, it may be asked whether this obligation of good faith in treaty negotiations is merely an aspect of an initial duty to negotiate (i.e, good

faith merely defines the obligation to negotiate) or whether the obligation to negotiate in good faith exists independently of any initial obligation to negotiate. In other words, is it the case that whenever negotiations take place (whether there is a duty to intervene or not), those negotiations must take place in good faith? It may be argued that it is the conclusion of a treaty that creates the obligation to act in good faith such that even in cases of obligations to negotiate in good faith, it is the creation of the prior international obligation to negotiate that brings the obligation to act in good faith into being. Good faith applies to all international negotiations as a moral standard of behavior [13]. It is natural that a measure of trust and good faith is present or developed between the negotiating parties; [14] however, whether from that place arises a legal obligation, a breach of which would be subject to sanctions, is the central question of the article.

The obligation to negotiate in good faith is of timeless relevance as negotiations are an everyday part of international relations. Good faith is a prerequisite for successful negotiations; it enhances the predictability of negotiating parties by reducing uncertainty and promoting an atmosphere of trust in negotiations [15]. It appears that the spying by Australia reported to have taken place is a breach by Australia of its customary international obligation of good faith. Good faith is a broad rule of international law. As the International Court of Justice has stated, "one of the basic principles governing the creation ... of legal obligations, whatever their source, is the principle of good faith" [16]. In the North Sea Continental Shelf Case, the International Court of Justice held that "good faith" underpinned the essence of negotiations related to seabed boundaries, [17] and, by implication, the resources of a disputed seabed. Good faith requires fair dealing between parties generally. In the context of treaty negotiations, it requires appropriate proceedings in creating negotiated legal obligations between the parties [18].

In the case of the CMATS treaty, Australia already had a vastly superior bargaining position with its long and sophisticated experience and expertise in diplomacy and the science relevant to reserves and apportionment. To seek a further upper hand by spying without more is the antithesis of good faith. While failure to negotiate in good faith is not a recognized ground of invalidity under the VCLT, it nevertheless provides Timor-Leste with a basis to seek the avoidance of the CMATS treaty. A breach of good faith in negotiations may have a vitiating effect under general principles of international law [19] or the customary law of treaties [20]. Although there is no clear standard for determining what constitutes a breach of good faith in treaty negotiations, the first principles indicate that a violation of good faith in the negotiation of a treaty exists. If a state intentionally seeks to deceive or to put the other party to an unfair advantage. For this reason, the commission of fraud in the negotiation of a treaty would be an instance of bad faith that renders a treaty invalid under the VCLT and null and void under general international law [21]. It depends, of course, on the terms of the arbitral tribunal. Still, a tribunal might issue a declaratory judgment finding the CMATS treaty null and void because of Australia's breach of good faith in its negotiation to let the parties know their relative legal positions [22]. Under Article 42, paragraph 1 of the VCLT, the invalidity of a treaty or a lack of consent to be bound by a treaty can only be established by the application of the provisions of the VCLT. As both Australia and Timor-Leste are parties to the VCLT, the grounds of invalidity that either party may advance appear to be limited to those set out in Articles 46-53 [23]. Articles 46-52 relate to conditions that make consent illusory (lack of competence or authority, error, fraud, and coercion). Article 53 concludes any treaty that conflicts with a peremptory norm. Bearing this particular focus of the VCLT in mind, an argument can be made that under general international law, an egregious breach of good faith in the negotiation of a treaty might serve to vitiate the treaty, notwithstanding Article 42(1) of the VCLT [24]. This is because such a breach of good faith strikes a fundamental precondition in establishing agreed international obligations. Without some minimum standard of good faith in the formation of negotiated commitment, the core idea of a global legal system underpinned, as it must be, at least formally, by mutuality and equality fails [25].

3.1. Espionage as a violation of the obligation of good faith in treaty negotiations

While no bright line test exists for what constitutes a breach of good faith in treaty negotiations, the principles indicate that an egregious violation of good faith in the negotiation of a treaty exists if a state intentionally seeks to dupe another party or put itself in a position of unfair advantage. For this reason, the commission of espionage in negotiating a treaty could be an instance of bad faith that can be invoked to render a treaty void under general international law[26]. It depends, of course, on the terms under which the arbitral tribunal will dispute between Timor-Leste and Australia (something we also do not know). Still, a tribunal might issue a declaratory judgment finding the CMATS treaty null and void because of Australia's breach of good faith in its negotiation to let the parties know their relative legal positions[27].

3.2. Intervention as a breach of the duty of good faith in negotiations

Suppose the reports about Australian espionage are accurate. In that case, an argument might be raised that Australia has breached international law by illegally intervening in the most intimate of internal affairs of Timor-Leste without its consent. This illegal intervention in the negotiation is a separate breach of good faith that might use as a basis for the legal avoidance of the treaty under general international law. U.N. General Assembly Resolution 53/101 on the principles and guidelines for international negotiations makes clear that during negotiations, "States have the duty not to intervene in matters within the domestic jurisdiction" of other states[28]. It would seem that deliberately sending spies into another form without permission to obtain confidential, privileged, secret, and classified information of the other state is just as much, if not a more significant intervention, into the exclusive sovereign domain of a state and is prohibited by international law. As the Permanent of ICJ highlighted in *Lotus*, "the first and foremost restriction imposed by international law upon a State is that failing the existence of a permissive rule to the contrary it may not exercise its power in any form in the territory of another State"[29].

Spying in another state without its consent[30] is an exercise of power by another that would appear to be prohibited. Despite repeated assertions from the United States and Australia that all states spy, I maintain that espionage without consent remains an illegal intervention where it occurs in the territory of another state or at inviolate premises[31]. Several obvious facts demonstrate this. Accordingly, if it can prove that Australia engaged in the alleged espionage, it would constitute another egregious breach of the obligation to negotiate in good faith. Suppose the arbitral tribunal has the power to issue declaratory relief. In that case, it may be possible for Timor-Leste to seek a declaration that CMATS is void if it can prove that during its negotiation, Australia violated its territorial sovereignty through covert action, pretenses, or disguise to obtain information concerning Timor-Leste's negotiation position or strategy.

IV. Research Methodology

This research applied qualitative research conducted as documentary research, reviewing studies, interviews and observation, and documents on concepts and theories concerning the implications for the maritime boundary negotiations between Australia and Timor-Leste. The current study used a legal approach. The researcher has explored international law and its implementing regulations. Data collection from various sources was analysed and compared with the context and conditions of the topic to obtain findings on the issues.

V. Conclusion

The arbitration under the Timor Sea Treaty raised the issue of whether espionage during treaty negotiations amounts to fraudulent conduct under Article 49 VCLT. Timor-Leste instituted arbitral proceedings against Australia at the Permanent Court of Arbitration 98, alleging the invalidity of the 2006 Treaty on Certain Maritime Arrangements in the Timor Sea on the grounds of fraud because Australia engaged in espionage in the course of negotiating the Treaty. It is allegedly the first case in which a state seeks invalidity of a treaty on the grounds of fraud. Timor-Leste also initiated proceedings against Australia in the ICJ but dropped the case after the ICJ had ordered provisional measures.

The ICJ found Australia's conduct to violate Timor-Leste's sovereignty and tagged Australia as a temporary measure. While the ICJ did not mention good faith, the principle of authority is relevant to good-faith international negotiations. One way to look at this dispute is as a complaint by Timor-Leste against an unequal treaty based on unequal bargaining power. Of course, the use of asymmetry in political and economic power to negotiate beneficial treaty terms is not presently a ground of invalidity under the law of treaties. However, the Final Act of the VCLT Conference includes a declaration condemning political and economic pressure use. The dispute between Timor-Leste and Australia over rights to resources in the seabed and subsoil below the sea between their coastlines. Having been closed out of the International Court of Justice, the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea, Timor-Leste is now seeking to arbitrate its dissatisfaction with current arrangements under a provision in the Treaty on Certain Maritime Arrangements in the Timor Sea (CMATS). Potential claims of fraud, breach of good faith, and unlawful intervention mean that it is likely that CMATS will be declared invalid or void. Much will depend on the evidence, however. Australia now finds itself in a difficult situation, and the dispute is likely to continue and fester, absent goodwill on the part of both parties. Allegations of fraud, breach of good faith, and unlawful intervention mean that it is likely that CMATS will be declared invalid or void. Much will depend on the evidence. Australia now finds itself in a difficult situation, and the dispute is likely to continue and fester, absent goodwill on the part of both parties. The justest course of action at this point could be to allow an independent third party to finally make a judicial determination of the seabed boundaries between Timor-Leste and Australia to achieve an equitable solution, create certainty about rights, and bring an end to this continuing saga.

References

- [1] Under these agreements, revenues in the JPDA are split 90% for Timor-Leste and 10% for Australia. Revenues in the Greater Sunrise area are split equally.
- [2] Art. 26, Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, 1155 UNTS 331.
- [3] Treaty between the Democratic Republic of Timor-Leste and Australia Establishing their Maritime Boundaries in the Timor Sea, New York, 6 March 2018 accessed 5 September 2022.
- [4] See Nick Miller, East Timor Seeks to Scrap Oil Treaty with Australia in The Hague over Spying Allegations, Sydney Morning Herald, December 6, 2013, available at: <http://www.smh.com.au/federal-politics/political-news/easttimorseeks-to-scrap-oil-treaty-with-australia-in-the-hague-over-spying-allegations-20131206-2yufv.html> See also Arbitration under the Timor Sea Treaty, 3 May 2013 (joint media release by the Australian Minister for Foreign Affairs and Special Minister of State), available at: http://foreignminister.gov.au/releases/2013/bc_mr_130503.html
- [5] Tanya Plibersek: Australia Must Restore 'Poisoned Relations' with Timor-Leste', The Guardian, 10 Feb 2016, available at: <https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetailsIII.aspx?src=TREATY&mtdsgno=XXI6&chapter=21&Temp=mtdsg3&lang=n>
- [6] Id.
- [7] See Matthew Craven, 'What Happened to Unequal Treaties? The Continuities of Informal Empire' (2005) 74 Nordic JIL 335.
- [8] M. E. Villiger opines that fraud is most likely to be limited to bilateral treaties. See M. E. Villiger. Commentary on the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties. Leiden, Boston: Martinus Nijhoff Publishers 2009, VCLT Article 49/3
- [9] Permanent Court of Arbitration. Arbitration under the Timor Sea Treaty (Timor-Leste v Australia). – <http://www.pcacases.com/web/view/37> (11 April 2016); K. Mitchell and D. Akande. Espionage & Good Faith in Treaty Negotiations: East Timor v Australia (20 septembre 2022). –

<http://www.ejiltalk.org/espionage-fraud-goodfaithin-treaty-negotiations-east-timor-v-australia-in-the-permanent-court-of-arbitration/> (11 septembre 2022)

[10] <http://www.smh.com.au/federal-politics/political-news/asio-raids-office-of-lawyer-bernard-collaery-over-easttimor-spy-claim2013120I-treaty-3-2yoxq.html>

[11] Paul Reuter, *Introduction to the Law of Treaties* (1989), 137-38

[12] Sarita Ryan, Australia's conflicted position in the Timor Sea, <http://rightnow.org.au/opinion-3/having-it-both-waysaustralias-conflicted-position-in-the-timor-sea/>.

Nuclear Test Case (Australia v. France), [1974] ICJ 253, 268. 18UNGA Res 53/101 (20 January 1999) UN Doc [13] A/RES/53/101, recital 8. 19 North Sea Continental Shelf Cases (FRG/Denmark; FRG/Netherlands), [1969] ICJ 3, 46-47

[14] H. Kelsen and the drafters of the Harvard Draft Convention recognised the moral but not the legal effect of the principle of good faith. See H. Kelsen. *The Law of the United Nations: a Critical Analysis of Its Fundamental Problems: with Supplement*. Union (NJ): Lawbook Exchange 2008, p 89; Harvard Law School. *Draft Convention on the Law of Treaties (Part III; Law of Treaties)*. – *American Journal of International Law, Supplement 1935/29* (hereinafter the Harvard Draft Convention), pp 780-781 as referred to in Hassan, pp 445- 446, 465.

[15] UNGA Res 53/101 (20 January 1999) UN Doc A/RES/53/101, recitals 4 and 7; K. Wellens. *Negotiations in the Case Law of the International Court of Justice. A Functional Analysis*. Farnham: Ashgate 2014, p 23; M. A. Rogoff. *The Obligation to Negotiate in International Law: Rules and Realities*. – *Michigan Journal of International Law* 1994/16, p 182.

[16] U. Lindell. *Modern Multilateral Negotiation: The Consensus Rule and Its Implications in International Conferences*. Lund: Studentlitteratur 1988, p 80.

[17] Nuclear Test Case (Australia v. France), [1974] ICJ 253, 268.

[18] UNGA Res 53/101 (20 January 1999) UN Doc A/RES/53/101, recital 8.

[19] North Sea Continental Shelf Cases (FRG/Denmark; FRG/Netherlands), [1969] ICJ 3, 46-47

[20] *Id.*, at 33.

[21] Additional grounds of treaty invalidity based on general principles of law or, to a lesser degree, based on the customary law of treaties outside the VCLT might be available in cases where the VCLT did not apply. See eg, Joe Verhoeven, 'Invalidity of Treaties: Anything New in/under the Vienna Conventions' in Enzo Cannizzaro, ed, *The Law of Treaties Beyond the Vienna Convention* (2011), 297-299 and n 6. This would not be the case between Timor-Leste and Australia because both are party to the VCLT and are limited to the VCLT's ground of invalidity.

[22] Bin Cheng, *General Principles of Law as Applied by International Courts and Tribunals* (1953), 158-160.

[23] A/RES/53/101(8 December 1998), available at:<http://www.un.org/Docs/asp/ws.asp?m=A/RES/53/101>.

[24] Bin Cheng, *supra* n. 20, at 160 (discussing fraud in the formation of an international tribunal as a violation of good faith that renders the entire proceedings null and void).

[25] Cf Christine Gray, *Judicial Remedies in International Law* (1990), 100-101.

[26] Paragraph 1(b), A/RES/53/101 (8 December 1998), available at: <http://www.un.org/Docs/asp/ws.asp?m=A/RES/53/101>.

[27] *S.S. Lotus (Fr. v. Turk.)*, 1927 P.C.I.J. (ser. A) No. 10, at 18 (1927) (Sept. 7) (emphasis added).

[28] Lord McNair, *the Law of Treaties* (1961), 553-554.

[29] Bin Cheng, *General Principles of Law as Applied by International Courts and Tribunals* (1953), 158-160.

[30] A clear form of permissible strategic observation by one state within the territory of another state arises under certain arms control agreements. See e.g. Art. XI(1), Treaty between the United States of America and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics on the Elimination of Intermediate-Range Missiles, 27 ILM 90, 95 (1988). If espionage in the territory of another state was legal at international law, then presumably there would be no need for inspection provisions in arms control and other treaties. Of course, this sort of consent to external observation does not allow for

or imply that covert observation beyond the overt observation expressly permitted under the treaty is allowed. 33 See Manuel R. Garcia-Mora, 'Treason, Sedition and Espionage as Political Offences Under the Law of Extradition' (1964) [31] U. PITT. L. REV. 65, 79-80 ("peacetime espionage is regarded as an international delinquency and a violation of international law"); John Kish, *International Law and Espionage* (1995), 88 ("the general principle of territorial sovereignty negates the permissibility of espionage in national territory [of another state]"). Other commentators take the view that espionage is prohibited by international law when it is criminalized by domestic legislation. See Quincy Wright, 'Espionage and the Doctrine of Non-Intervention in Internal Affairs', in Roland J. Stanger, ed., *Essays on Espionage and International Law* (1962) 12-13. If this were the case, then foreign espionage is illegal in Timor-Leste because it is protected against under the Government Decree Law on the Intelligence System of the Democratic Republic of East Timor (13 Septembere 2022), available at: http://www.eastimorlawjournal.org/Government_Decree_Laws_East_Timor/intelligence_system.html

Author name: Dr R. Herman Katimin, S.Sos., S.H., M.Si., M.H.

Lecturer of the master of Law Study Program, Galuh Ciamis University, Indonesia

Email: hermankatimin.unigal@gmail.com

Co-author name: Rakotoarivelo Tiana Nantenaina, S.H., M.H.

Lawyer, Graduated in Master's degree of International Law, the Faculty of law, Padjadjaran University Bandung, Indonesia.

Email: tiananantenaina5@gmail.com, rakotoarivelo18001@mail.unpad.ac.id

